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Cite this article: Korten H, Steffan-Dewenter I. 2026 Drought events reduce reproductive success of a long-tongued bumblebee species. *Proc. R. Soc. B* **293**: 20253056.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2025.3056>

Received: 27 November 2025

Accepted: 27 February 2026

Subject Category:

Ecology

Subject Area:

ecology

Keywords:

drought, climate change, conservation, pollen and nectar resources, reproductive success, pollinator ecology, bumblebees, *Bombus pascuorum*

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Electronic supplementary material is available online at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.8375158>.

Drought events reduce reproductive success of a long-tongued bumblebee species

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Climate change challenges pollinators through rising temperatures, altered precipitation regimes and an increased frequency of extreme weather events. Droughts are becoming more frequent and severe, with largely unknown effects on pollinator fitness and associated ecosystem services. In a large-scale field experiment, we compared colony performance of a long-tongued non-commercially bred bumblebee species between a drought year and a year with average climatic conditions. Colonies established from wild queens were placed in 25 high-quality semi-natural grasslands and either received sugar-water supplementation or did not to evaluate resource limitation. Colony lifespan was shorter in the drought year, and both colony weight and reproductive output (male and queen numbers) were strongly reduced. Sugar-water supplementation enhanced male production and colony weight only during drought, suggesting that nectar scarcity limits colony performance to some extent during dry periods. However, queen production was unaffected, and when comparing fed colonies between years, those in the drought year performed much worse, implying crucial pollen limitation. We conclude that increasingly frequent droughts pose a major threat to bumblebee populations and the pollination services they provide, even in flower-rich protected areas. Adaptive conservation management could enhance tree shade in open grasslands and promote wetlands for extended water retention during droughts.

1. Introduction

Animal pollination is a crucial ecosystem service for maintaining agricultural yields and global biodiversity [1–3]. However, pollinators are declining due to a variety of interacting factors, like habitat loss and fragmentation, pesticide use, pathogens or alien species [3,4]. In recent years, increasing attention has also been directed towards the impact of climate change [5,6]. Pollinator populations must cope with rising average temperatures, altered precipitation patterns and extreme weather events [7,8]. The frequency and severity of heatwaves and droughts have already increased, with future scenarios predicting further amplifications [9,10]. Climate change can directly affect pollinators by influencing their physiology or behaviour [11]. Indirect effects mostly concern resources, e.g. when shifts in flowering phenology create seasonal mismatches or gaps in floral resources, thereby altering nectar and pollen availability for pollinators [12,13]. Studies on the impacts of droughts on pollinators have primarily focused on these plant-mediated effects on floral traits and resource availability [14–16]. Water limitation can reduce flower size and number, as well as nectar and pollen quantity or quality, thereby decreasing floral attractiveness [15,17]. These changes can reduce pollinator visitation rates and alter community composition, ultimately

leading to lower pollination success [18,19], but direct fitness consequences for pollinator species have rarely been assessed.

Bumblebees are among the most important and abundant pollinators in temperate regions of the Northern Hemisphere [20]. They are central-place foragers; hence, they depend on flowering resources in the surroundings of the nest. Nectar serves as their source of carbohydrates, especially for energy-intensive processes such as flight or thermoregulation [21]. Pollen, on the other hand, is mainly used as a protein source for the brood [20]. The lack of floral resources can lead to reduced colony growth and reproduction [22–25], but little is known about the individual effects of nectar and pollen limitation, especially in the context of climate change. Bumblebees are well adapted to moderate and especially lower temperatures, due to their furry body and the ability to thermoregulate [21,26]. As central place foragers, they are bound to the local climatic conditions and resource availability in the area around the nest after its establishment [27]. These traits make bumblebees particularly vulnerable to increasing temperatures and extreme weather events [28]. This vulnerability is already reflected in recent declines and range contractions of bumblebee populations, which have been (at least partly) linked to climate warming [29,30]. Projections of future climate scenarios even suggest that many species will face extinction at regional to global scales [31–33].

Extreme weather events, such as heatwaves and droughts, which often co-occur, expose bumblebees to multiple stressors. Heatwaves can have direct negative effects on parasite resistance and antibacterial immunity of bumblebees [34], detection of floral scents [35], larval weight gain and survival [36,37] and thermoregulation of the nest [38,39]. Further, indirect effects can occur due to reduced pollen and nectar production of flowering plants [14,40,41], leading to a negative effect on bumblebee foraging [19,40,42]. Direct effects of drought on individual bumblebee colonies are unknown, but a multi-year field study found that nest density dropped by approximately 40% in drought years [43]. Moreover, a strong negative relationship between drought intensity and site occupancy was revealed for *Bombus occidentalis* in North America [44], while long-term monitoring in California linked local bumblebee declines partly to drought-driven reductions in floral resources [45]. These studies add to the growing evidence of reduced bumblebee abundances after local droughts and heatwaves [46].

Although these different aspects have been studied or can be inferred, the actual effect of extreme weather events has never been investigated at the colony level, let alone in the field. The most accurate method of determining any specific effects on bumblebee populations is the establishment of experimental colonies in the field [47]. This way, the colony growth and, most importantly, the reproductive success can be measured directly. Care must be taken when selecting the study species, as the most often used *Bombus terrestris* has been shown to be more resistant to different stressors compared with other species, most notably to heat stress [48–50]. It is, therefore, not a suitable representative for other bumblebee species, particularly in the context of climate change research, and other species should be prioritized instead [51,52].

Here, we investigated the impact of extreme drought events, commonly linked to climate change, on bumblebee colonies in a large-scale field experiment. We compared colony development and reproductive success measured as the number of males and queens produced by bumblebee colonies in a drought year with a year with average climatic conditions. We established colonies from locally wild-caught queens of *B. pascuorum*, a long-tongued bumblebee species of the ‘pocket-maker’ group that was successfully reared and used in a field study for the first time. The colonies were placed in high-quality semi-natural grasslands and assigned to either a sugar-water feeding treatment or no feeding to disentangle the role of pollen and nectar limitation under drought and ambient conditions. We hypothesized that (i) droughts have a negative effect on colony survival, development and reproduction, (ii) feeding of sugar water (as an unlimited nectar substitute) mitigates negative impacts of drought conditions, and (iii) pollen resources limit colony development and reproduction.

2. Material and methods

(a) Study area/experimental design

The study was conducted in Franconia (Germany). The area is characterized by arable agriculture, fragmented semi-natural habitats (e.g. calcareous grassland) as well as forest and settlement areas. We selected calcareous grasslands as study sites, which are high-quality and flower-rich habitats for bees [53]. In 2022, we selected 14 calcareous grasslands, and in 2024 we selected 20 sites, of which 9 were the same as in 2022 (figure 1). At each study site, we placed wooden nesting boxes with a bumblebee colony (three in 2022 and two in 2024, for a total of 82 boxes). Nesting boxes were placed in shady spots to prevent overheating in summer. Each box was either equipped with a bottle of sugar water close to the entrance throughout the season or remained without such artificial food supply so that in each site, at least one colony was fed and one was not fed at all.

Bumblebees exhibit two distinct brood-rearing strategies [54]. The first group, referred to as ‘pollen storers’ (typically short-tongued species), constructs pollen pots in which pollen is stored, and bumblebees directly feed the larvae from these reserves. The second group, the ‘pocket makers’ (usually long-tongued species), deposit pollen in pockets adjacent to the brood, from which the larvae feed themselves. We used *B. pascuorum*, a long-tongued pocket maker that usually builds nests above ground, as our study species [55].

(b) Establishment of colonies

In April 2022 and 2024, *B. pascuorum* queens were caught in the study region and placed in rearing boxes in a climate chamber. After visual screening for ectoparasites, they were constantly supplied with sugar water and fresh pollen and reared following [56]. As soon as the colony size reached a minimum of three workers and additional brood cells were close to hatching, they were transferred into the wooden nesting boxes placed in the field (from early May to early June). The transferred colonies had 5.0 ± 2.5 adult workers and a colony weight of 6.8 ± 1.5 g (± 0.1 g; Mettler Toledo PM 3000, Mettler Toledo, Columbus, OH, USA).

Figure 1. Overview of the study setup. (A,B) One of the calcareous grasslands used as study sites (A) during the summer of the drought year in 2022 and (B) in 2024, with average weather conditions. (C) Location of the study region of Franconia (Bavaria) highlighted on a map of Germany (© Natural Earth, [naturalearthdata.com](https://www.naturalearthdata.com)). (D) Bumblebee nesting boxes deployed at each site, with (right) and without (left) sugar-water supplementation. (E) A colony of the study species *Bombus pascuorum* in a nesting box.

A total number of 77 colonies (2022: $n = 40$ [fed: $n = 16$; not fed: $n = 24$]; 2024: $n = 37$ [fed: $n = 18$; not fed: $n = 19$]; five excluded due to destruction or early queen death) were successfully established over both years. Further details on colony rearing and establishment are provided in the methods section of electronic supplementary material, file S1.

(c) Data collection (monitoring in the field)

After successful establishment of the colonies in the field, they were monitored throughout the season, starting in mid-June. We recorded colony weight to the nearest 0.1 g using a precision balance (Mettler Toledo PM 3000, Mettler Toledo, Columbus, OH, USA) and assessed the maximum weight ('peak weight') as a measure of colony development. In addition, we measured the reproductive success by counting the queens and males in the colony, regularly took photos of the nests and screened the nests for parasite infestation. These measurements were done either weekly (2022) or monthly (2024). Monitoring was stopped when the season came to an end (i.e. colonies lost weight and only had queen and male brood cells left). In 2022, this was at the end of August, while in 2024, it was at the end of September. A colony was declared dead once no living bumblebees remained in the nest. More detailed descriptions of colony monitoring and data collection can be found in the methods section of electronic supplementary material, file S1.

(d) Weather data

To evaluate the climatic conditions, we assessed the precipitation, soil moisture and number of hot days for each of our sites in the respective year. Daily precipitation data for each site were accessed in R through the 'rdwd' package using RADOLAN data [57]. RADOLAN provides spatially (resolution of 1 km²) and temporally highly resolved hourly precipitation data by combining the values measured at the precipitation stations with the precipitation data collected by weather radars (DWD Climate Data Centre). The number of hot days (max. air temperature of at least 30.0°C) was assessed from DWD data in the same way. Soil moisture conditions were obtained from the drought monitor for Germany (UFZ Drought Monitor/Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research) with a spatial resolution of 4 km² [58,59]. The soil moisture index (SMI) quantifies anomalies by referencing the current soil moisture as the percentile rank against historical records from 1951 to 2015. Daily SMI data for total soil (1.8 m) and topsoil (uppermost 25 cm) were extracted for each site in R using the 'ncdf4' package [60]. The entire workflow for obtaining the drought parameters, as well as further information on the origin of the data, including the R script, can be found in the methods section of electronic supplementary material, file S1.

To quantify weather conditions for a time period that is relevant for colony development, we selected data from 1 May to 31 August based on observed colony phenology (electronic supplementary material, figure S1). As the two defined seasons differed greatly in total precipitation, total-soil SMI, top-soil SMI and number of hot days, we refer to 2022 as 'drought year' and 2024 as 'normal year' (figure 2A; electronic supplementary material, figures S3 and S4). To place both field seasons in

Figure 2. (A) Seasonal soil moisture conditions across the 25 field sites during the ‘drought season’ (2022, red) and the ‘normal season’ (2024, blue), based on the soil moisture index (SMI) for total soil (0–1.8 m). The SMI reflects the percentile rank of current soil moisture relative to the historical (1951–2015) baseline. Each thin line represents one site, and bold lines depict the mean for each year. Shaded grey areas denote drought classes (UFZ Drought Monitor/Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research). The displayed period (1 May–31 August) corresponds to the key period of colony development. (B) Historical annual mean SMI (1950–2024), calculated as the average across all field sites. The drought season (2022) and normal season (2024) are highlighted as red and blue dots, respectively. The dotted line (SMI = 0.5) represents the long-term median soil moisture level.

a long-term context, we additionally calculated annual mean total-soil SMI values for the period 1950–2024 (see electronic supplementary material, file S1 for details; figure 2B).

(e) Statistical analysis

Effects of drought and feeding on bumblebee colony development were tested with generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMM). The response variables were peak colony weight and the two indicators of reproductive success: the number of produced males and queens. We created a separate model for these three parameters with the same predictors. The predictor variables were year (drought versus normal) and feeding treatment (fed versus not fed). We also included the interaction of those two variables and study site as a random factor. To account for a possible effect of the timing of transfer of the colonies in the field, we included the date when the colonies were transferred to the field as a fixed factor in our models. This variable (day of year) was scaled to improve model convergence. To account for differences in variance between feeding treatment and years, we included a dispersion formula with the interaction of both factors ($\text{dispformula} = \sim \text{year} \times \text{feeding}$). This allows the variance to vary as a function of these predictors, improving model fit and addressing heteroscedasticity. All models were fitted using a Tweedie distribution with a log link to account for the non-negative, right-skewed response data. By tuning a single power parameter, the Tweedie distribution smoothly transitions between Gaussian, Poisson and gamma distributions, adapting to different data structures. The model fit was checked in terms of linearity, collinearity, normality of residuals, normality of random effects and overall model fit via posterior predictive check. The models for males and queens were checked for zero inflation. For group comparison, we extracted and compared estimated marginal means for each year \times feeding combination based on fitted models. To evaluate differences in colony survival across year \times feeding combinations, Kaplan–Meier survival curves were generated, and we performed pairwise log-rank tests with Holm correction for multiple pairwise comparisons.

All statistical analyses were conducted in RStudio 2024.12.0 [61] with R 4.2.2 [62]. We used the R packages *readxl* [63] and *dplyr* [64] for data import and handling. GLMMs were constructed using *glmmTMB* [65], with model summaries assessed using *car* [66]. The model fit was evaluated using *DHARMA* [67] and *performance* [68]. Estimated marginal means were calculated with *emmeans* [69], and model estimates were extracted using *broom.mixed* [70]. For survival analysis, we used *survival* [71], *survminer* [72] and *lubridate* [73]. All plots were generated with *ggplot2* [74]. The complete R script is provided in the electronic supplementary material.

Figure 3. Kaplan–Meier curves of colony survival in the ‘drought year’ (red) and ‘normal year’ (blue), with solid lines representing fed and dashed lines unfed colonies. The plus icon marks the end of the experiment in the respective year. Colonies died earlier in the drought compared with the normal year (log-rank test, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 4. Mean peak colony weight (g) with 95% confidence intervals for colonies of *B. pascuorum* in a ‘drought year’ (red) and ‘normal year’ (blue) that were either not fed or had ad libitum access to sugar water. Letters at the top indicate significant differences between groups based on estimated marginal means from generalized linear mixed-effects models.

3. Results

In comparison with the long-term climate record of our study region, the 2022 field season represents a pronounced drought year, while 2024 reflects near-average conditions (figure 2B). Droughts of similar intensity have been recorded historically, but were generally rare. Over the last 15 years, however, drought years have become more frequent.

Two-thirds (67%) of all colonies successfully reproduced. Among these, about 60% produced both males and queens, just over one-third (36%) produced only males, and approximately 4% (two colonies) produced only queens. In the drought year, less than half of the colonies reproduced (45%), of which half (50%) produced only males, 39% produced both castes and 11% produced only queens. In contrast, during the normal year, most colonies (91%) reproduced, with about three-quarters (72%) producing both males and queens, and roughly one quarter (28%) producing only males, while none produced queens only. The colony that produced the greatest number of queens (96) also reached the highest maximum weight (434 g). Male production peaked in a different colony, with 85 males.

(a) Colony survival

There was no significant difference in colony survival between both feeding treatments within each year (2022: $p = 0.371$; 2024: $p = 0.371$, electronic supplementary material, table S1). However, strong differences were found between years, as colonies died earlier during the drought year ($p < 0.001$; figure 3; electronic supplementary material, tables S1 and S2). More specifically, fed colonies had lower survival rates during the drought year compared with fed colonies in the normal year ($p < 0.001$), and the same was true for unfed colonies ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 5. Mean reproductive output of *B. pascuorum* colonies shown as the number of (A) males and (B) queens produced ($\pm 95\%$ CI) in a drought year (red) and normal year (blue), with colonies either unfed or supplied with sugar water ad libitum. Different letters denote significant group differences according to estimated marginal means from generalized linear mixed-effects models. Bee pictograms are obtained from <http://phylopic.org> (for details, see electronic supplementary material).

(b) Peak weight

Drought conditions and supplementary sugar-water feeding had a strong effect on bumblebee colony peak weight (figure 4; electronic supplementary material, figures S7 and S8, tables S4–S7). In the drought year, peak weight was much lower compared with the normal year ($p < 0.001$, estimate: 1.00, 95% CI: [0.42, 1.58]). Likewise, supplementary feeding strongly increased the overall peak colony weight ($p < 0.001$, estimate: -1.58 , 95% CI: [-2.25 , -0.91]). Furthermore, there was an interactive effect between drought conditions and feeding ($p < 0.001$, estimate: 1.32, 95% CI: [0.56, 2.07]), indicating a year-dependent feeding response.

Most notably, fed colonies gained more weight in the normal year compared with the drought year ($p = 0.004$, estimate: -1.00 , 95% CI: [-1.76 , -0.24]), as the mean peak weight increased from 67 to 182 g—an approximately 2.7-fold increase (+172%). In non-fed colonies, the increase was even more pronounced ($p < 0.001$, estimate: -2.32 , 95% CI: [-3.03 , -1.60]): from an average of 14 to 140 g—a 10.1-fold increase (+909%). Further, feeding of sugar water had a positive effect during the drought year ($p < 0.001$, estimate: 1.58, 95% CI: [0.70, 2.45]), so fed colonies reached, on average, a fivefold heavier peak weight than non-fed colonies (+383%, 14 versus 67 g). In the normal year, however, feeding had no significant effect ($p = 0.480$, estimate: 0.26, 95% CI: [-0.21 , 0.73]) and the average peak weight was only slightly increased by approximately 1.3-fold (+30%, 140 versus 182 g).

The date of colony transfer to the field had no effect on peak weight ($p = 0.223$, estimate: -0.125 , 95% CI: [-0.33 , 0.08]).

(c) Males

Male production was strongly affected by both drought conditions and supplementary sugar-water feeding (figure 5; electronic supplementary material, figures S7 and S8, tables S4–S7). The number of males produced was significantly higher in the normal year than in the drought year ($p = 0.002$, estimate: 1.12, 95% CI: [0.43, 1.82]). Feeding also had a strong positive effect ($p = 0.006$, estimate = -1.47 , 95% CI: [-2.51 , -0.43]). The interaction between year and feeding showed a marginal trend ($p = 0.080$, estimate = 1.03, 95% CI [-0.12 , 2.18]), pointing to a year-dependent feeding response.

Notably, fed colonies produced far more males in the normal year than in the drought year ($p = 0.009$, estimate: -1.12 , 95% CI: [-2.04 , -0.21]), with mean male numbers increasing from 13.5 to 41.5—a 3.1-fold increase (+208%). This effect was even more pronounced in non-fed colonies, which increased from an average of 3.1 to 26.7 individuals (8.6-fold, +760%, $p < 0.001$, estimate: -2.15 , 95% CI: [-3.36 , -0.94]). Supplementary feeding enhanced male production under drought conditions ($p = 0.029$, estimate: 1.47, 95% CI: [0.10, 2.83]), increasing the average number of males from 3.1 to 13.5 individuals (+334%, 4.3-fold). In contrast, during the normal year, feeding had no significant effect ($p = 0.281$, estimate: 0.44, 95% CI: [-0.19 , 1.08]), with a modest increase from 26.7 to 41.5 individuals (+56%, 1.6-fold).

No effect of the date of colony transfer was detected ($p = 0.863$, estimate: -0.02 , 95% CI: [-0.24 , 0.20]).

(d) Queens

Queen production was only affected by drought conditions, but not by supplementary sugar-water feeding (figure 5; electronic supplementary material, figures S7 and S8, tables S4–S7). Colonies produced markedly more queens in the normal year compared with the drought year ($p < 0.001$, estimate: 2.75, 95% CI: [1.66, 3.83]). Feeding, however, had no significant impact ($p = 0.169$, estimate: -1.06 , 95% CI: [-2.58 , 0.45]), nor was there an interactive effect between year and feeding ($p = 0.392$, estimate: 0.74, 95% CI: [-0.95 , 2.43]).

Notably, fed colonies produced far more queens in the normal year than under drought conditions ($p < 0.001$, estimate: -2.75 , 95% CI: $[-4.17, -1.33]$), with mean queen numbers increasing from 1.2 to 18.6—a 15.6-fold increase (+1460%). The difference was even greater among non-fed colonies, which rose from 0.4 to 13.5 queens (32.7-fold, +3170%, $p < 0.001$, estimate: -3.49 , 95% CI: $[-5.25, -1.73]$). Supplementary feeding did not significantly increase queen production under drought ($p = 0.515$, estimate: 1.07, 95% CI: $[-0.92, 3.05]$) or normal conditions ($p = 0.867$, estimate: 0.33, 95% CI: $[-0.75, 1.40]$), with only minor increases from 0.4 to 1.2 (+190%, 2.9-fold) and from 13.5 to 18.6 (+38%, 1.4-fold).

The date of colony transfer to the field showed no influence ($p = 0.964$, estimate: 0.01, 95% CI: $[-0.39, 0.41]$).

4. Discussion

In a two-year field experiment, we examined the impact of a severe drought event on the colony performance of a common but understudied bumblebee species. The drought year was an exceptionally dry season within the historical context of our study region, while the normal year reflected near-average climatic conditions. Drought significantly reduced colony survival, weight gain and, most critically, reproductive success measured as the number of males and queens produced. Supplementary feeding with sugar water enhanced colony growth and male production, but mainly during drought, highlighting nectar scarcity as a limiting factor under dry conditions. Queen production was, however, not increased by feeding in either year. This, along with the severe negative drought effect on fed colonies, points to even more critical pollen limitation during drought. These findings have important implications for pollination services and bumblebee population declines, especially as climate change increases the frequency and severity of drought events.

(a) Effects of drought events on bumblebee colonies

The drought event had a strong negative impact on the overall colony performance, as colonies gained less weight, showed lower reproductive success of both males and queens and died earlier. In addition, in the drought year, almost no queens were produced, and colonies that managed to reproduce primarily produced males—a typical indicator of resource scarcity, since queen production requires substantially greater resource investment than male production [75]. Queens are the sole individuals that establish new colonies in the next season and therefore have a much higher reproductive value. Consequently, the near-complete failure of queen production during drought is likely to substantially weaken the size of bumblebee populations in the subsequent year.

Previous studies have mostly focused on the physiological effects of extreme weather, and primarily on heatwaves rather than droughts [34–39], though both often co-occur. The primary drought impact may be indirect via plant responses: water stress reduces flower size, abundance and attractiveness to pollinators [14,19,41], and most importantly, nectar and pollen production [14,41]. Consequently, bumblebees forage less [19,40,42], gather fewer resources and colonies develop more slowly. Bumblebee colonies only maintain short-term reserves [20,21], so prolonged droughts can lead to starvation of adults (nectar) and brood (pollen), potentially causing colony collapse, as observed in our study. This may also explain both the reduced bumblebee nesting densities in drought years [43] and the lower abundances observed after droughts [46]. In addition, droughts and the heat events often associated with them can have direct physiological impacts. Heat reduces immune function [34], floral scent detection [35], larval development [37] and can cause adult mortality when thermal tolerance thresholds are reached [49]. Nest cooling via fanning is energetically costly (i.e. nectar-demanding [21]), further depleting resources [38,39]. Altogether, droughts probably reduce colony success through both direct and especially indirect pathways. To better understand the contribution of each, it is essential to experimentally isolate the role of resource limitation, which we did by implementing a supplementary feeding approach.

(b) Resource limitations

Feeding sugar water to simulate an unlimited nectar supply enhanced colony growth and male production during drought but had no significant effect in the normal year. This suggests that nectar availability limited colony success to a certain extent. In line with this, exceptionally high nectar depletion rates of around 95% were recorded on calcareous grasslands in the study region during the drought, supporting severe nectar limitation [76]. If nectar—the sole source of carbohydrates for energy-intensive tasks like foraging—is scarce, workers may be forced to limit their foraging range, duration and frequency, leading to less collected pollen and ultimately slowing colony growth, as shown in our unfed colonies. It may also cause adult starvation, directly weakening the colony. The production of queens—the most important reproductive unit—was, however, not affected by feeding in either year and was therefore primarily limited by pollen. Furthermore, colonies fed with sugar water still performed much worse in the drought than in the normal year, indicating that feeding did not fully compensate for drought effects, and pollen was strongly limited during drought. Therefore, pollen availability can be emphasized as key to colony success and especially reproduction. The reduction of pollen quantity is probably the main factor limiting colony success under drought conditions. However, pollen quality and diversity can also decline, as only drought-tolerant plant species may continue producing pollen under water stress, potentially adding to nutritional constraints of colonies [77,78].

Interestingly, we found no evidence of nectar limitation in the normal year, in contrast to previous findings showing that supplementary sugar-water feeding enhanced colony success of *B. terrestris* in agricultural landscapes [25]. In semi-natural grasslands, resources for *B. pascuorum* thus appear to be less limited under average climatic conditions, possibly due to high floral resource availability in these high-quality habitats and because pollen, rather than nectar, is the limiting factor.

Our findings align with studies showing both nectar and pollen are essential for colony development [22–25], but we were able to disentangle the two factors. Nectar fuels energetic demands, and pollen drives brood production. Our results suggest that both are restricted during drought and together limit colony success, but pollen is more important, especially for reproduction. Interestingly, feeding did not improve colony survival in either year, suggesting that pollen scarcity was too severe to support brood development during drought, even when nectar needs were met.

(c) Breeding long-tongued bumblebees

For the first time, we successfully established field colonies of a long-tongued, pocket-making bumblebee species. We reared colonies of the common and widespread *B. pascuorum* in the lab from locally wild-caught queens, while all previous studies predominantly used the commercially bred *B. terrestris*, and rarely other biologically very similar ‘pollen storer’ species. *B. terrestris* is ubiquitous, short-tongued, able to fly long distances to forage, uses a very wide range of flowers, builds exceptionally large colonies [55,79] and is much more resilient to different stress factors compared with other bumblebee species, e.g. in terms of heat stress [48–50]. Therefore, *B. terrestris* is not a good representative of the entire genus *Bombus*, and species with a different biology should be prioritized to counteract the bias towards *B. terrestris* [51,52,80]. *B. pascuorum* has a short foraging range, small nests and a different diet, like most of the other long-tongued species [55,79,81]. Long-tongued pocket makers account for roughly half of the bumblebee species in Bavaria, yet this guild has never been used in experimental studies with colonies. They even comprise the majority of threatened species (82%), indicating a high vulnerability compared with short-tongued pollen storers (18%). Owing to their long tongues, they pollinate a distinct plant community, underscoring their ecological importance. We endorse utilizing long-tongued pocket maker species for future studies and recommend *B. pascuorum* as a suitable model species.

(d) Implications and future perspectives

We observed a strong negative drought effect despite the study taking place in high-quality semi-natural grasslands, where floral abundance and diversity are generally high [82]. This suggests even stronger effects in lower quality habitats. Moreover, our study species is common and widespread [55], and therefore benefits from a stable metapopulation that may facilitate recovery and even adaptation after drought events. In contrast, rare species adapted to specific habitats may suffer genetic bottlenecks or local extinction after a drought event [83], especially as many already have low genetic diversity [84,85]. Whether the impact of drought is reinforced by other stressors, such as pesticides, is currently unknown. Future studies should explore these potential interactions. A possible adaptation of bumblebees to more common droughts might involve shifting the life cycle to end earlier, avoiding midsummer droughts. This could be particularly important since summer droughts coincide with periods of low natural resource availability in the landscape [86,87].

Bumblebees are key pollinators in temperate regions of the Northern Hemisphere [20]. The collapse of their populations due to droughts could have far-reaching implications for crop yields, wild plant communities and ecosystem stability. It is unclear whether pollination services after drought events can be compensated for by more drought-tolerant pollinators, especially given the typically high abundance of bumblebees in many habitats. Populations are already declining, partly due to climate change [29,30], and our results provide direct experimental support for drought as a critical driver. Given the predicted future increase in drought frequency and severity [9,10], our findings indicate an urgent threat and support predictions of dramatic future reductions in bumblebee populations [31–33].

From a management perspective, one solution might be to promote drought-resistant, summer-flowering plant species in agricultural environmental schemes, like flower fields, to ensure nectar and pollen availability during dry periods. Urban habitats could mitigate drought effects through artificial irrigation, but they may introduce additional stressors such as higher ambient temperatures [88]. Habitats that are less susceptible to drought will become increasingly valuable for bumblebee conservation. In semi-natural grasslands, conservation management can be adapted to allow a higher density of shade trees, as such microhabitats could provide cooler and moister conditions for bumblebees during periods of heat and drought. Similarly, forests and forest gaps have the potential to offer buffering microclimatic conditions [89,90]. Wetlands represent another habitat type of potential future importance, as these will probably provide adequate water for plants even during dry periods. Given their potential to buffer drought effects, management practices should focus on enhancing their suitability for bumblebees and other pollinators. In addition, landscape-scale measures aimed at increasing water retention could help mitigate drought impacts on floral resources and therefore on pollinators. Creating drought-resistant microhabitats and focusing conservation efforts on habitat types that buffer drought effects could create important refuges for bumblebees during increasingly frequent dry periods. In conclusion, our study reveals the severe impacts of drought events on a long-tongued bumble species and underpins the need for adaptive conservation management in semi-natural high-value grassland habitats.

Ethics. All required permits for capturing wild queens, conducting work in protected habitats and placing bumblebee colonies in the field were obtained from the governments of Upper and Lower Franconia (permit numbers ROF-SG55.1-8646.1-7-364-2 and RUF-55.1.2-8646.7-4-42-8).

Data accessibility. Data and R code are available as part of the electronic supplementary material [91].

Declaration of AI use. We used AI-assisted tools to support data visualizations in R; all other aspects of the study were conducted without AI.

Authors' contributions. H.K.: conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; I.S.-D.: conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, supervision, writing—review and editing.

Both authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

Conflict of interest declaration. We declare we have no competing interests.

Funding. This study is part of the project 'Safeguard' which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003476.

Acknowledgements. We thank Laura Flöck and Sophia Heinlein for helping with bumblebee rearing in the lab and for assistance in the field. We are also grateful to Carolin Biegerl for selecting the study sites within the Safeguard Project and to Fabian Bötzl for assistance with statistics. Our thanks further go to Jean-Léonard Stör for helping set up the bumblebee boxes, and to one anonymous reviewer for helpful comments on the first manuscript.

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